

IoT Based: River Water Quality Monitoring System

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ABSTRACT

Water quality is a critical factor affecting public health, agriculture, aquaculture, and the environment. Traditional water monitoring techniques are time-consuming and inefficient for real-time tracking. This paper proposes an IoT-based smart surveillance system using an ESP32 microcontroller integrated with various sensors (pH, temperature, turbidity and TDS). The system offers real-time data acquisition and cloud-based monitoring via a web interface. The proposed solution enhances responsiveness and decision-making, ensuring timely intervention against contamination threats. The quality of water continuously using IoT devices like ESP32 has a connected built-in Wi-Fi module that enables internet access and sends sensor data measurements to the Cloud. To evaluate the quality of water from aquatic bodies, a number of sensors are employed to monitor a variety of factors. To determine if the water is appropriate or not, the results are saved in the cloud.

Keywords: Water Quality, IoT, ESP32, Real-Time Monitoring, Cloud, pH, TDS, Turbidity.

INTRODUCTION

Maintaining water quality is essential in ensuring human health and protecting ecosystems. Traditional methods are labor-intensive and prone to delays. The adoption of IoT provides an efficient solution to automate, digitize, and scale up water quality monitoring. This research presents a smart river monitoring system leveraging the ESP32 microcontroller and multiple sensors, enabling real-time data visualization and analysis via the cloud.

Fresh Water Management is crucial in Bangladesh due to the country's rapidly growing population, which calls for an increase in agricultural, industrial, and other requirements. Fresh water's "chemical, physical, and biological" makeup defines its quality. Keeping an eye on the water's quality aids in pollution detection pollution, harmful chemicals, and water. The classic approach, which is still popular today, comprises gathering water samples, evaluating them in a lab, and providing advise on any water treatment measures. There are three basic processes in the current system for monitoring water pollution. Water sampling Sample testing Research analysis. These three methods are all very expensive, challenging, time-consuming, require professional counsel, and are not particularly effective. Hence, rather than relying on a human procedure, automation may now be added to water quality monitoring in order to take the right action. Hence, some technical innovation has crept into the automation of water quality monitoring, helping to monitor water quality rather of depending on human processes. Due to the indiscriminate discharge of untreated effluents into the local low-lying lands and proximity to the textile, bleaching, and dyeing factories, the shallow aquifers there and around are extremely polluted. We created a model to assess water sources, and we then uploaded and analyzed the data online. The foundation of this is a wireless communication system. Such communication systems have a huge economic value, and as wireless sensor networks continue to expand and more nations demonstrate tremendous interest in curiosity. When water quality parameters deviate from the predefined set of standard values, the system will additionally alert the remote user.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. The development of cost-effective water quality monitoring systems has become essential for rural and remote areas where conventional infrastructure is often unavailable. One approach introduced an affordable sensor cloud-based solution designed to monitor key parameters such as pH, turbidity, and temperature. This system uses low-cost sensors to collect data and transfers it to the cloud for storage and analysis, offering a scalable and efficient option for underserved regions.
2. Expand on this concept, They developed an IoT-based water quality monitoring system that integrates real-time sensing with cloud data storage. Their approach used multiple sensors, including those for pH, turbidity, and temperature, to assess water parameters. The data was transmitted via the internet to a centralized platform, enabling remote and real-time monitoring. Their work underscores how IoT technologies can bridge the gap between rural needs and modern digital monitoring solutions.
3. The role of Internet 4.0 technologies. They discussed how interconnected sensor networks can be leveraged for environmental monitoring, including water quality. This research provided insight into the use of intelligent networking and automation to enhance the efficiency and scalability of monitoring systems in both urban and remote settings.
4. Further advancements in smart water management have led to the integration of cyber-physical systems (CPS) with IoT technologies. These systems provide real-time monitoring, event detection, and predictive analysis capabilities. The architecture supports decision-making processes, allowing early intervention in the case of potential water quality issues, thereby improving overall resource management.
5. A separate water quality monitoring system emphasized importance of immediate pollutant detection. By continuously observing critical parameters such as pH, turbidity, temperature, TDC, water flow the system is capable of triggering instant alerts when any deviation from the normal range is detected. This allows for quick corrective actions and helps prevent long-term environmental and health impacts.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND BLOCK DIAGRAM

ESP32 38PIN Development Board:

Dual-core 32-bit Xtensa LX6 processor, up to 240 MHz.

Integrated Wi-Fi (802.11 b/g/n) and Bluetooth 4.2 + BLE.

32 GPIO pins for versatile input/output operations.

Multiple communication interfaces: UART, SPI, I2C, PWM, ADC, DAC.

12-bit ADC (up to 18 channels) for analog sensor interfacing.

2× 8-bit DAC for audio or analog signal output.

Ultra-low-power consumption modes for battery-based applications.

Micro-USB port for easy programming and power supply.

Flash memory: Typically 4MB for storing code and data.

pH Sensor:

Operating Voltage: 5V DC

Operating current: 5-10mA

pH Concentration Range: 0-14 pH

pH < 7 Water is Acidic.

pH > 7 Water is Basic.

pH = 7 Water is Neutral.

Operating Temperature: 0C to 80C

Max Stability Time: 60 seconds

Analog Voltage Signal Output

Storage Temperature Range -20°C~ 90°C

Rated Current Max. 30 mA

Insulation Resistance Min 100 MΩ by 500V DC

The sensor operates on the principle that when light is passed through a sample of water, the amount of light transmitted through the sample dependent on the amount of soil in the water. As the soil level increases, the amount of transmitted light decreases.

Flow Sensor:

Temperature Sensor (DS18B20):

Measures temperature from -55°C to +125°C with good accuracy ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$).

Works with 3.0V to 5.5V – Can be powered by different voltage sources, making it flexible

Provides 9 to 12-bit resolution, meaning it can give detailed temperature readings.

Takes 750 milliseconds (0.75 seconds) to give a temperature reading.

This is YF-S201 Water Flow Measurement Sensor with 1-30Liter/min Flow Rate – Black.

This Sensor Sits In Line With Your Water Line And Contains A Pinwheel Sensor To Measure How Much Liquid Has Moved Through It.

Analog Signal As Output.

TDS Sensor:

Turbidity Sensor:

Operating Temperature Range -10°C ~ 90°C

It can measure the total dissolved solids in a solution

Analog Signal, easy to implement

Power indication LED

Support 3.3/5V Input Voltage

0 ~ 2.3V Output Voltage can be easily implemented in 3.3/5V control system

Waterproof TDS Probe.

It is indeed built using a combination of **sensors**, a **ESP32 MCU** with inbuilt **Wi-Fi module**. Here's a breakdown of how these components come together to form the system:

Sensors:

pH Sensor: Measures the acidity or alkalinity of the water, which is crucial for the health of aquatic life.

Turbidity Sensor: Monitors water clarity, which indicates the amount of suspended particles and pollutants.

Water flow Sensor: Tracks the flow of water.

Temperature Sensor: Measures water temperature, as it affects chemical processes and the health of aquatic ecosystems.

TDS Sensor: Total Dissolved Solids measures concentration of dissolved solids in water.

ESP32 (Microcontroller Unit):

ESP32 is a series of low-cost, low-power system-on-chip microcontrollers with integrated Wi-Fi and dual-mode Bluetooth. Commonly found either on device specific PCBs or on a range of development boards with GPIO pins and various connectors depending on the model and manufacturer of the board.

Data Flow and Communication:

Sensors collect water quality data from the river in real time.

The ESP32 microcontroller unit processes and filters the data, sending it to the cloud for storage and further analysis.

Real-time data is accessible through a cloud-based dashboard, where users can monitor water quality, receive alerts, and review historical data.

on the ESP32 microcontroller. The system monitors and sends real-time data about different water quality parameters continuously over a wireless communication platform to a cloud platform for users to access and monitor water conditions remotely.

A collection of six sensors is interfaced with the ESP32 board:

The TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) sensor monitors the concentration of dissolved impurities and ions in water.

The pH sensor monitors the alkalinity or acidity of water, important for drinking, agricultural, and industrial purposes.

The Turbidity sensor measures the amount of suspended particles in the water, reflecting clarity and possible contamination.

The Temperature sensor monitors the temperature of the water, which may influence chemical properties and sensor values.

The Water Flow sensor reports the rate at which water is flowing, suitable for detecting leaks or tracking usage.

The Conductivity sensor reads the capacity of water to pass electricity, proportional to its ions and salinity.

These sensors transmit analog or digital signals to the ESP32, which processes the information and utilizes its onboard Wi-Fi module to send the data to a cloud platform like Ubidots STEM. The data is saved in the cloud and presented on a web-based dashboard in a user-friendly manner with charts, tables, and alerts

The webpage can be accessed remotely through a computer or smartphone to monitor live sensor readings and trends in historical data. This configuration aids in the early detection of pollution, guaranteeing water safety and enabling sustainable water management.

The system is energy-efficient, low-cost, and scalable, making it ideal for numerous applications such as smart agriculture, aquaculture, drinking water systems, and environmental monitoring.

Fig: Block diagram water quality monitoring system

The block diagram shows a complete IoT-based water quality monitoring system based

Parameters	Range
pH	6.5-8.5
Turbidity	1-5
TDS	0-900
Temperature	17-30

METHODOLOGY

A river water quality monitoring system using ESP32 works by collecting water quality data from sensors, processing it, and storing it in a web application:

The components are mounted on floating setup. Different sensors will collect real time data from water and send data to ESP32 microcontroller.

ESP32 will compare data with threshold values and store data on cloud. Through web page end user can access the real time water quality parameters.

Collect data: Sensors such as a pH meter, turbidity sensor, flow sensor, TDS sensor and conductivity sensor measure water quality parameters.

Process data: The ESP32 microcontroller collects and processes the data from the sensors.

Store data: The data is sent to a web application where it can be stored.

The ESP32 is often used in water quality monitoring systems because it has low power consumption and built-in Wi-Fi. The system can be used to monitor water quality in real-time and can be used in large and local bodies of water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ideal number for water purifiers is almost always close to 7. Since it is the same as the pH of mammalian mucous membranes and eyes. Lemon water with a low pH level is bad for human health because it can irritate the skin and hurt the eyes if it gets in them. Other disinfectants won't be as effective as they were for higher pH values as a consequence of this low pH value. While basic water has a pH number greater than 7.5. Extremely Basic water that contains calcium hydroxides is unsafe for human consumption.

Fig: Filtered Water

Turbidity parameter's value, which demonstrates to us that turbidity is a significant component for both aquatic and terrestrial organisms. It's safe to consume anything with a value under 5 NTU. We noticed that the water coming from the filter is always between 2 and 3 NTU. As a result, it is safe to consume. The temperature of the water is also a significant element for the human body, as well as for agriculture and aquatic organisms. As we can

see, the usual weather ranges between 17 and 30 degrees Celsius. TDS of drinking water lies between 0-900. So TDS of water under 900 is considered to be safe for drinking.

Fig: Lemonade Water

CONCLUSION

Finally, the project proves successful in the development and deployment of a real-time water quality monitoring system based on the ESP32 microcontroller and Internet of Things technologies. With the integration of several sensors such as temperature, pH, turbidity, TDS, and flow sensors, the system has the ability to monitor essential water quality parameters continuously with high accuracy. The data obtained from these sensors is wirelessly transmitted to the Ubidots STEM platform, facilitating remote visualization, real-time updating, and threshold-based alerting.

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